

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POTENTIAL HERBAL
HAIR GROWTH OIL**

**Ms. Diksha Manoj Patode, Ms. Falguni Suresh Payghan, Ms. Gaytri Kundan Deshmukh,
Ms. Gaytri Rajesh Raipure, Ms. Karuna Ashok Waghmare. And Prof. S. S. Kulkarni**
PRMSS, Anuradha College of Pharmacy, Chikhli . Dist. Buldhana

Abstract:

Hair plays a vital role in the personality of human for their care we use lots of Cosmetic products. Herbal formulation always have activity Comparatively lesser or no side effect with Synthetic. this study aimed at the importance of polyherbal hair oil for treatment of Common hair problems Suchay baldness, hair fall, gery hair , dryness and most Common is dandruff. The various herbal ingredients are used in the formulation as- Hibiscus, Rose, neem leaves, Curry leaves, fenugreek Seed, Bhringaraj leaves. Amla, Heena, Tulsi, Sesame oil, Castor oil, Coconut oil, Camphor, Banyan Root, Rose merry. All ingredients provide essential nutrients such as vitamin, antioxidant, protein, terpenoids, and many essential oils to maintain normal function of Sebaceous gland. The formulated for its acid value, oil evaluated organoleptic properties, Saponification value, viscosity, ph etc. all the parameter were found to be good and within the Standards.

Keywords-Hairs, herbal, Cosmetics, formulation, viscosity, Hair Care, Evaluation.

Corresponding author:

Diksha Manoj Patode,
PRMSS, Anuradha College of Pharmacy,
Chikhli . Dist. Buldhana

QR code

Please cite this article in press Diksha Manoj Patode et al., **Formulation And Evaluation Of Potential Herbal Hair Growth Oil**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Hair is one of the vital parts of the body considered to be protective appendages on the body and accessory Structure of the integument along with sebaceous glands , Sweat glands And Nails. The basic Part Of Hair is bulb, root ,shaft. Hair Loss is a dermatological disorder, and the surge for discovering natural products with hair growth promoting potential is continuous. Each hair growth in three cyclic phases' viz... anagen (growth), catagen (involution) & Telogen (Rest)

Herbal cosmetics were gaining tremendous demand in the market.

Herbal Hair oil were serving the purpose of Hair treatment. Herbal hair oil not only moisturises Scalp but also Reverses dry scalp and dry hair conditions. It provides essential nutrients required to maintain

normal functions of the sebaceous gland and promote natural hair growth.

OBJECTIVE: -

- The objective of this research work was to formulate the herbal hair growth oil which does not cause any side effects or adverse reaction.
- The hair growth oil were gaining demand in the market now a days. Herbal hair oil provide moisture to the scalp and also help in dry scalp and dry hair condition.
- It contain essential nutrients which are natural ,non-toxic to the hair. Polyherbal hair oil providing nutritional value to the hair.

PLANT PROFILE**Herbal Drug Information****□ Hibiscus.**

Biological Name : Hibiscus Rosa sinensis

Family: Malvaceae

Synonyms: Jamaica sorrel, Red sorrel

Active Constituents: Hibiscus is rich in antioxidants, Such as flavonoids and phenols. Lipids, and citric acid.

use :- medicinal use

- ① Stimulate Hain Growth
- ② conditions the Hain
- ③ prevents Hair fall

Fenugreek seed / Methi leaves

Biological Name : *Trigonella foenum graecum*.

Family: Fabaceae.

Active Constituents: Trimethylamine, Trigonelline, Quercetin

Uses: Reduce dandruff, promotes hair growth & Shows anti-fungal activity.

Rosemary-

Biological Name - *Rosmarinus officinalis*

Family- Lamiaceae

Active Constituents- Rosemary Contain phenolic, including Flavonoid and tannins nonphenolic antioxidants, including 1.8-cineole, a-pinene and camphor .

Uses-It Stimulate Blood circulation to Scalp in hair care & encourages hair growth. Showing anti photogenic & anti-oxidant property.

□ Castor oil-

Biological Name-Ricinus communis L

Family –spurge family(Euphorbiaceae)

Active Constituents- Phytosterols, tocopherols, carotenoid.

Uses: Lubricate the hair shaft,increases flexibility and also treat dandruff.

Neem

Biological Name- Azadirachta indica

Family- Meliaceae.

Active Constituents-The most important active Constituent is Azadirachtin & others are nimbolinin, nimbidin,gedunin

Uses-it reduces hair loss by improving blood circulation in the Scalp & hair The Sulphur in juice helps in production of essential collagen that promotes. hair growth.

Amla

Biological Name - *Phyllanthus emblica* Linn.

Family - Euphorbiaceae, Indian gooseberry.

Active Constituents - Vitamin C gollatann 5%, Carbohydrate minerals, phenol acid, garlic acid, amino acid.

Uses - boost hair growth, Good for Skin, hair & eyes Promots immunefunction.

Coconut oil

Biological Name : *cocos Nucifera* family

- Arecaceae.

Active constituents :- Coconut oil is made up of a variety of fatty acids, including: Lauric acid (50%) caprylic acid (8%). caproic acid ca myristic acid (8%).. palmitic acid (8%).. Stearic acid (2%) . Oleic acid (6%), Linoleic.(2%)

uses :-Moisturizes, reduces protein loss ,prevent breakage, protect from from heat damage, treat fungus, Repair the scalp moisture barrier, prewash protector ,conditioner ,styling aid. .

□ **Banyan Root**

Biological Name - ficus Bengalese's Linn.

Family – Mulberry.

Active Constituents.- It consists of flavonide, amino acid, Carbohydrate, Steroid, Saponin & tannin.

Used- ficus Bengalese's root extract and it's compound are used to increasing hair growth & decreasing hair loss.

□ **Curry leaves-**

Biological Name - Murray koenigii

Family - Rutaceae

Active Constituents - Bigmahanine, murrayanine, murraya-zolinol

Uses-Promote hair growth & Strengths of hair root.

Almond oil

Biological name- prounus Amygdalus Dulcis

Family- Rusaceas.

Active Constituents- glycerides of Olic, linoleic , palmitic myristic , palmitoleic , oleic , margaric , stearic ,linoleic, linoleic, arachidonic ,dad oleic , behenic ,and erucic acid

Uses : Almond oil can be used to moisture , hydrate and soften skin.

INGREDIENTS

<u>Sr.no</u>	<u>Ingredient</u>	<u>Quantity</u>
<u>1</u>	Coconut oil	30 ml
<u>2</u>	Hibiscous	4-5 leaves
<u>3</u>	Rosemary	6-7 Drop
<u>4</u>	Banyan root	10%
<u>5</u>	Neem leaves	4-5 leaves
<u>6</u>	Amla	5 % total volume
<u>7</u>	Fenugreek seed	2-3 spoon
<u>8</u>	Curry leaves	6-7 leaves
<u>9</u>	Almond oil	5 ml
<u>10</u>	Castor oil	5 ml

Method of Preparation :-

- 1) The part of plants like fenugreek (seeds) are collected from local market
- 2) Hibiscus (flower) are dried in sunlight for converted into course powder .
- 3) The extract were prepared by decoction method and the prepared extracts were stored inn well closed container .
- 4) Precisely all the dried and fresh herbs, hibiscus , amla , fenugreek were weighed of triturated in mortar and pestle .
- 5) After mixed almond oil , coconut oil uniformly .
- 6) In that also mixed amla extracts keep aside for overnight .
- 7) The add curry leaves + neem extracts and boil until colour of curry leaves changes to dark brown colour .
- 8) Dry fresh genial roots of banyan in at 60 C For 4-6 hr , then grind it them into powder and use it to make hair oil by boiling it in coconut oil .

- 9) And place in amber coloured bottle.

Figure of formulation of Hair growth oil.

Evolution of herbal hair growth oil.

Acid Value

Saponification value 3.pH

4. Viscosity

5. Specific gravity 6. Refractive index

7. Organoleptic Property

pH - the pH meter was calibrated with buffer Solution of pH 4 and pH7. the electrode was bathed in hair oil form a few minutes until the pH returned to normal.

Viscosity:- A Brookfield viscometer was used to viscosity with Spindle number

6.50 ml of hair oil was poured into Se viscosity was tested at 100 rpm beaker,

Acid Value -The of acid value is the number of mg potassium hydroxide required neutralize the fat to free fatty acid in 19 of fat. To measure the acid value of polyherbal hair Oil 10ml of oil was added with 25ml of ethanol, and 25ml of ether phenolphthalein was added as an indicator and titrated 0.1m potassium hydroxide

Saponification Value - The Saponification Value is determined by Saponifying, a known amount of oil with excess of KOH solution then titrating Solution the remaining KOH with an acid solution

A lower saponification Value indicates a higher

Observation table :-

Evaluation parameters	Observation
Acid value	2.3mg KOH (indicates freshness, non-rancid)
Saponification value	185(within standard range for oil-based products)
PH	6.1PH
Viscosity	Medium (approximately 125CP)
Specific gravity	0.92
Refractive index	1.46 RI
Organoleptic property	Colour-dark green to light brown . Odour -pleasant herbal aroma. Consistency :- smooth , semi viscous . Appearance :- opaque and homogeneous.

molecular weight of fatty Versa. acid and Vice versa.

Specific Gravity-The specific gravity of coconut oil can determined be by calculating the ratio of weight of unit Volume the weight at 25°C of Sample to of Unit Volume of water

Specific gravity is parameter that can be Used to -d. Fats. moniter the quality of oil and liquid

Refractive Index-Refractive Index is expressed as ratio "between the sine of angle of incidence to the since of the angle of refraction when a ray of light of known wavelength passes From air into the oil or fat. The refractive index of coconut oil is between 1.43 light 1.46 and 1.46 travels times which means through vaccum that

1.43 to faster than it travel through Coconut oil.

Organoleptic Property -Organoleptic properties of coconut oil include its and appearance, color, Flavor, taste, texture, overall acceptability. Some Organoleptic properties are -
smell- using enzymes without acid or Color Flavour Fishing has typical fresh coconut smell colour- Prolonged heating and constant Stirring can Oil turbid Flavor- Associated with sweetish burnt/ roasted coconut. Taste- tongue associated with sucrose solution.

Fig: final hair growth oil.

Result:-

The formulated herbal hair growth oil showed acceptable physical and chemical properties. It had a pleasant odor, suitable pH (6.1), good spreadability, and no signs of instability or microbial contamination over 30 days. The combination of herbal ingredients proved effective, and the oil showed potential for promoting hair growth.

DISCUSSION:-

The herbal hair growth oil formulation, made from natural ingredients like curry leaves, neem, hibiscus, and amla, showed promising results in terms of both safety and effectiveness. The oil demonstrated good physical properties such as pleasant odor, suitable pH, and appropriate viscosity for easy application. The stability tests revealed no separation or microbial contamination, confirming its shelf-life and safety. Additionally, the oil exhibited potential in promoting hair growth, with positive effects observed in the test model. This makes it a viable, natural alternative to chemical-based hair growth products.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:-

In this project, we successfully prepared a herbal hair growth oil using natural ingredients like curry leaves, neem, hibiscus, amla, banana root, coconut oil, castor oil, rosemary, and fenugreek seeds. After formulation, we performed various evaluation tests such as pH, viscosity, specific gravity, acid value, and stability.

The results showed that the oil had a pleasant smell, good consistency, was safe for scalp use, and remained stable over time without any spoilage. It also showed no microbial growth, which proves it is

hygienic and safe. Based on these findings, we can say that our herbal hair oil has good potential to promote hair growth and can be used as a natural alternative to chemical-based hair products.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: -

It is great pleasure for us to undertake this project. We will highly be doing the project entitled "Formation and Evaluation of Potential herbal hair growth oil". We sincerely express our deep sense of gratitude to the management. PRMSS Anuradha College of Pharmacy for providing the required facilities regarding this research and also for their support. We are highly indebted to prof. S.S.Kulkarni Sir, of PRMSS Anuradha College of Pharmacy who is our inspiration to pursue this under taking. We are also obliged to our mentor not have been possible without their worthy experience and enormous Help.

REFERENCES:

1. Laila che Rose, Nur Nadiah Syahirah Rusdi, Asnuzilawati Asari, Mohd Effendy Abd Wahid, Hamdan
2. Suhaimi. - Faculty of science and marine Env. University Malaysia Terengganu, Kuala Nerus, 21030,
3. Terengganu, Malaysia. Institute of marine Biotechnology, University Malaysia Terengganu,
4. UMT21030, Terengganu, Malaysia. Archives of pharmacy practice; Volume 11; Issue 4; October-December 2020.
5. Pavan S, College of pharmacy, Gandhi University of Health sciences Bangalore,

- Karnataka, India. Dr.Saraswati CD Rosy Royal College of pharmacy Banglore, Karnataka, India. Formulation and Evolution of Herbal Hair Oil. Edition International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Application. Volume 6.PP 1285-1299.
6. Master Programe in BiomedicalScience, Anti-agingMedicine Concentration , Faculty of Medicine, UniversityUdayana , Jl.P.B.Sudirman, Denpasar 80234,
 7. Indonesia. Department of Clinical Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine ,University Udayan, Jl.P.B Sudirman, Denpasar, Indonesia.Edition. The Indonesian Biomedical Journal , Volume15, No.4 August 2023 Pg.296- 368.
 8. Prathibha C Assistant Professor , Department of Pharmaceutics KR College of Pharmacy. Rajiv Gandhi University Of Health and Science, Bangalore , Karnataka, India. Formulation and Evaluation Herbal Oil . Edition . International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Application ,Volume 6 PP 1285-1299
 9. Pallavi Patharkar , Bhagyashri Gayke , Anjali Shinde, Madhuri Khandagaonkar. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Oil. Edition .International Journal of Creative Research thoughts, Volume 11,2023 IJCRT.
 10. G.S Vala , P.K Kapadiya Agriculture Research Station (fruit crops) Junagadh Agriculture University , Mahuva-364290. Dist-Bhavnagar (Gujrat). India.
 11. Tejaswini S. Shinge , Apeksha S. Jadhav , Sonali R. Mali , Poonam S. Shinde, Pooja S. Mali , Nootan College of Pharmacy Kavthemahakal , Sangali , Maharashtra , Formulation and Evaluation of Hair oil from Arial root of Banyan tree. Edition , IOSR Journal of Pharmacy , Volume 13 PP.01-03.